

SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS AS EXPROPRIATED INVESTORS

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Annotation

It is no secret that in recent years the influence of social networks on people's lives has increased significantly. In the process, social networks with millions of users managed to collect a large amount of personal data on their servers. Refusal to share users' personal information has led social media platforms to suspend their activities in some countries. In this case, it is a scientific problem to determine whether there is a fact of violation of the rights of social media platforms as investors. This essay aims to analyze the infraction of the rights of social media platforms as investors, the expropriation of their property, the measures taken by host states against them.

Key words: social media platforms, personal data, infraction of the rights, expropriation, investor, host state.

1. Introduction.

1.1. Since the beginning of the century, the role of social media platforms in people's lives has been constantly growing and it has become incredibly important to this day. With its growth, a new type of legal problem began to arise in society. In particular, social media platforms that came out with a large amount of personal information from their clients were forced to suspend their activities in many countries because they did not want to share this information. And this trend is forcing us to reconsider the scientific views formed in relation to such concepts as investment, investment relations between investors-host states and adapt them to

business models like social media platforms¹. Nowadays, we often encounter cases of internet censorship and internet blocking. Several countries have increased various pressures on social media platforms aiming to avoid their communities possible social crises caused by misinformation on the internet. In the process, countries are trying to enact the necessary laws in order to regulate the activities of social media platforms. Consider the blockage of LinkedIn in Russia taking after the company's disappointment to tolerate by the information maintenance law². Free speech advocates claim that open order concerns were not the driving force behind the ban, but this hasn't stopped Russia from pressuring other sites, like Facebook and Twitter, to support the controversial law³. As a result of the surge in terrorist attacks nationwide and the struggle against them, the Sri Lankan government prohibited the use of various social media sites, including Facebook, in April 2019. Other nations throughout the world are following suit, including Germany⁴ and India⁵. On the one hand, the rights of social media platforms as investors, expropriation of their property should be analyzed and on the other hand, the measures taken by the host countries against these types of business models should be questioned.

2. Materials and methods.

2.1. A few methods and literature can offer assistance us analyze the most issues of this essay. During our analysis, we use historical, comparative-legal, logical and factual strategies. Moreover, the ICSID Conventions, which entered into constrain in 1965 and 2022, regulations of arbitration centers, arbitral awards

¹ Vivek Sharma & Shreya Jha, "Social Media platforms as expropriated investors. Reviewing state measures from the perspective of international investment law", *Völkerrechtsblog*, 3 December 2019, doi: 10.17176/2019451203-180702-0.

² LinkedIn blocked by Russian authorities, *British Broadcasting Corporation* (Nov. 17, 2016), <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-3801454501>.

³ Marc Bennetts, Facebook and Twitter could be blocked in Russia in data storage row, *The Guardian* (Apr. 17, 2019), https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/apr/17/facebook-and-twitter-face-russian-sanctions-in-data-storage-row/*//.

⁴ Germany: The Act to Improve Enforcement of the Law in Social Networks, Article 19 (Aug. 2017), <https://www.article19.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/170901-Legal-Analysis-German-NetzDG-Act.pdf> [‘Article 19’].

⁵ India considering blocking Facebook, WhatsApp, *New York Post* (Aug. 7, 2018), <https://nypost.com/2018/08/07/india-considering-blocking-facebook-whatsapp/>.

and scientific doctrines, UNCTAD Series on Issues in International Investment Agreements II offer assistance us in our analysis of universal traditions. The most recognized materials for the settlement of venture debate between social stages and have states are the ICSID Conventions and UNCTAD Series on Issues in International Investment Agreements II.

3. Results.

3.1. Social media platforms as investors. The use of the international investment arbitration system by investors in protecting their rights is a common occurrence in international private law. Usually investors can apply for international investment arbitration with a claim based on the following documents:

- international contracts;
- bilateral investment treaties (BIT);
- multilateral investment treaties (MIT);

In arrange to start such an arbitration, resources belonging to social media platforms will have to correspond to the internationally recognized concept of "investment". It is a worldwide hone to broadly interpret "investment" made by an enterprise. The prerequisites to be satisfied in arrange to qualify as an investment beneath the Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States (ICSID Convention) are commitments in cash or other resources, a certain length, a component of chance, an operation made in arrange to create a financial movement within the host state, assets contributed in accordance with the laws of the have state and bona fide investments of assets. The tribunal had emphasized⁶ that "an extensive scrutiny of all these requirements is not always necessary, as they are most often fulfilled on their face, overlapping or implicitly contained in others." Therefore, opening a subsidiary business and establishing a local office to hire staff to handle the execution of local initiatives by

⁶ ICSID Case No. ARB/06/5

a corporation that owns a social media platform should be viewed as an investment. Additionally, the traditional definition of what makes up a property for a foreign firm has undergone major revision. Social media networks' capital may be divided into two categories:

- tangible resources;
- intangible resources.

Tangible resources are those that are tangible and already exist. They are valuable economically or commercially. This might include things like structures, machinery, and stock.

The intangible or electronic commodities of networks of social media however, constitute their greatest significant benefit. Digital assets are all forms of content that are registered in the system and have value for the business. Digital assets for social media platforms are their user bases and the data they produce. Contracts and subscriptions are also considered assets in investment arbitration. Both tangible and intangible assets have been seen to be subject to expropriation. Social media platforms have just become popular a decade back, yet they have quickly grown to be a multi-billion-dollar industry. These phenomena have been described as remarkable and accurately represents this particular type of company structure. These portals connect the needs of several client groups that are interdependent. Basically, they generate income by leasing out areas for marketing, interacting with software developers, and most importantly selling customer data to marketers. Moreover, these systems do not need a substantial amount of physical resources. Users' primary asset, which is also a component of their digital assets, is the information they collect. In this sense, the social media platforms make a smaller investment relative to the benefits they receive. Because this has already been acknowledged worldwide, it is clear that for social media platforms, the quantity spent and the worth of the investment's return are not necessarily proportionate.

3.2. Restrictions imposed by the government on social media sites.

There have already been cases when governments have taken action against global social media platforms because of concerns about privacy, private information, client contact, and preserving public stability. The European Court of Human Rights determined that Turkey's banning of YouTube infringed the freedom of speech rights in the case of *Cengiz and Others v. Turkey*⁷. YouTube was intermittently restricted in Turkey from 2008 and 2016. The website's commercial possibilities are impacted by such persistent blocking. On the contrary side, there is growing support for direct investment from abroad in the information technology industry, with several nations inviting international information technology businesses to invest in their regions. It is crucial to remember that situations like this serve as the foundation for reasonable expectations. Lawmakers of a nation might raise reasonable expectations by declaring that they would adhere to a specific political current and take the required steps to support it. As a result, it might be assumed that a restriction on communication technology businesses following such pronouncements may go against genuine expectations. Expropriation may be considered when such expectations are violated. Expropriation describes when the government has a justifiable reason to seize private property for public use. For this type of expropriation, the investor must get compensation. You may find a thorough research here⁸. Social media platforms should elevate concerns about state action towards them to the status of an investor-state dispute and seek compensation in light of Turkey's YouTube ban. It is essential that the state intervention deprive social media platforms of significant and long-lasting economic benefits. Expropriation cannot be considered when such platforms are momentarily blocked. However, these platforms are considered to have been expropriated by the government if the deprivation was brought on by a brief prohibition that effectively neutralized their properties. Governments

⁷ Global Freedom of Expression | *Chengiz v. Turkey* - Global Freedom of Expression <https://globalfreedomofexpression.columbia.edu/cases/cengiz-v-1-turkey/>

⁸ <https://globalfreedomofexpression.columbia.edu/cases/cengiz-v-turkey-251/>

occasionally adopt rules that are neutral toward businesses and are done so in good conscience. In the state of Jammu and Kashmir, for instance, the Indian government disabled a number of social networking sites when the constitution's extremely contentious Article 370 was repealed. The home detention of the political opponents also caused a commotion in the Indian parliament. No website for social media could be accessible by anyone in that state owing to the internet restriction. The government asserted that the restriction was required because these websites have frequently been utilized by terrorist organizations to disseminate separatist material. Such legislation may be considered expropriation and may violate clear expectations. In addition, expropriation requires that a right granted by the host state be rendered worthless in order for an action taken by an external authority to have a significant impact on its legal advantages. Such judgments are extremely fact-specific and difficult to generalize.

4. Discussion.

4.1. It is widely accepted that, in accordance with the norms of international customary law, governments have an inherent right to control matters falling under their purview because of their territorial integrity⁹. Treaty law acknowledges these policing abilities; it only outlines the effects of these kind of actions without ever really contesting the authority to expropriate¹⁰. The majority of BIT regimes have, however, placed some requirements for the lawful use of police authorities. These include non - discrimination, common interest, and, in some cases, fair trials. Any expropriation claim must at the very least satisfy these requirements. The determination of whether the challenged blockage meets the expropriation threshold must be made at the beginning since a factual study of these three factors will always be required.

4.2. It should be noted that, as stated in *Metalclad v. Mexico*, the rule on expropriation encompasses any “covert or incidental interference” with the use or

⁹ Christoph Schreuer & Rudolf Dolzer, *Principles of International Investment Law* 98 (2008).

¹⁰ UNCTAD Series on Issues in International Investment Agreements II, United Nations Conference on Trade and Development 8 (2012), https://unctad.org/en/Docs/unctaddiaeia2011d7_en.pdf [‘UNCTAD’].

pleasure of the capital in alongside direct or official revenues of real property. Arbitral institutions, like the one in *Telenor v. Hungary*, have recognized “intensity” and “duration” as the two primary determining factors in the test to prove an indirect expropriation. The social media businesses must show that the contested blockade significantly robbed them of their capital in order to pass the test's first component. It suffices for the governmental intervention to have interfered with the investment’s “usage or control these risks economic gain” for the impact to be considered significant. Since click-based adverts and promotions are the foundation of social media firms’ whole business models, they only make money when their platforms are usable. Upon blocking, these businesses may contend that the limitation interferes significantly (if not entirely) with their ability to profit from their invest. Availability to consumer markets is another point that may be made. In *Pope & Talbot v. Canada*, the Tribunal determined that the foreign investor’s “capacity to sell” softwood lumber to the US market was crucial to the operation of the company and as a result was a property that could be taken by force. Share of the market and consumer access were also determined to be assets subject to expropriation by the *Chemutra v. Canada* Arbitration. It might be claimed that a blockade deprives the social networking firm of its major investment capital since the existence of its user base is essential to the industry. In addition to having access to users, these “assets” also include their ownership of the domain name and ensuing “interest” in user data. This attraction generally leads from a binding and may be considered a contractual right, which would be protected if the investment clauses were written broadly enough to cover interests like “claims to money” or “rights in the sphere of intellectual property, technical processes, and know-how”.

4.3. The timing of the barrier would be the subject of the second component of the expropriation test. Arbitral institutions have interpreted the criteria to mean that the influence of a remedy must be greater than “merely transitory” because each intervention cannot constitute to expropriation. *S.D. Myers v. Canada* may be

used by the host governments to claim that a blocking of just a week or ten days is only a “stay of execution of advantages” and not a “denial”. This argument, however, is readily refuted. It didn't matter much if the process was delayed by a few months in Myers because the firm hadn't yet begun operations there. In fact, the Tribunal accepted that the damages brought on by the increase in competition during this time period may be taken into consideration for determining damages. It's fascinating to observe that the Tribunal added that under some conditions and circumstances, even “temporary or partial deprivations” might constitute expropriation. Since a “lasting” deprivation is no longer necessary for it to be permanent, it will thus be advantageous for a social media business to prove that the blockade was in place for a fair amount of time.

5. Conclusion.

5.1. The earlier parts show how a new business model has emerged, bringing with it a unique set of legal complications. When these issues are handled on a global scale, questions arise about how social media platforms should be viewed against the backdrop of the present investor-state dispute system. A tribunal must adjust its traditional jurisdiction toward this new area when comparing the host state's right to uphold peace and order on its territory against the aspirations of a social media platform to do business. The investor must be paid for the loss of chance to generate money because an arbitration panel cannot be allowed to determine whether periods of a prohibition were arbitrarily imposed and because the state has the legislative right to make decisions about problems of internal peace and security.

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